

TNT Soccer Simulation 2D Team Description Paper 2024

Daniel Salami¹, Radman Ghourchian², Mohammad Saleh Hamrahi³, Mohammad Sadra Hamrahi³ and Farzin Hasanzade⁴

¹ Salam Sadegh High School, Iran

² Yahyazade1 School, Iran

³ Mandegar Alborz high school, Iran

⁴ Salam Darabad High School, Iran

Danielalhk8@gmail.com,

Hasanzadefazin97@gmail.com, mohammadsadrahamrahi.1386@gamil.com, saleh.hamrahi1386@gmail.com, ghourchianradman@gmail.com

Abstract. The RoboCup competitions hold various leagues, and the Soccer Simulation 2D League is a major one among them. Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) match involves two teams, including 11 players and a coach, competing against each other. The players can only communicate with the Soccer Simulation Server during the game. In this report, the technical method and We explain the simulation steps for 2D football simulation of TNT team. IranOpen2023 was the first competition that TNT team participated in and we got a very good result and we definitely had many problems that we tried to solve a part of it this year. Our team focused more on how players move and attack strategically. In this report, we describe what problems we solved this year and what areas we paid special attention to .

Keywords: RoboCup, Soccer Simulation, Defense Strategy.

1 Introduction

RoboCup has hosted annual robotic soccer competitions since 1997, following the proposal of robotic soccer games as a new research topic in 1992. The primary objective of these competitions is to advance the robotics and artificial intelligence field by implementing robotic soccer games. Several leagues, including rescue, soccer simulation, and standard platform soccer, have been created to achieve this.

The Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) league is one of the oldest RoboCup leagues. In a soccer simulation 2D game, two teams containing 11 players and one coach compete against each other. Each game takes 6000cycles(10minutes). In each cycle, the players and coach receive observations from the RoboCup Soccer Simulation Server and send actions based on those observations back to the server. The server is responsible for controlling the game.

1.1 Related Work

Year after year, teams use algorithms to help develop the SS2D league and make it stronger.. One of these algorithms is Player'sMatchUp. Helios has developed an algorithm called Player's MatchUp for exchanging players' positions during a game. Oxy used the RSA accumulator(Real-World Performance of Cryptographic Accumulators) to model opponents strategy by using the observation coach.

1.2 Previous Work

The TNT team was formed in 2022 and started working. We started from the Agent base and developed it. At first, we faced many problems that we were able to solve over time. Iran Open 2023 was the first competition in which TNT participated and we placed fifth, which was more than we expected, which really motivated us. Also, our team qualified for the 2023 RoboCup held in France, which we could not participate in for a number of reasons.

2 Pass

Passing is one of the most important behaviors in Soccer Simulation 2D because

It is one of the most effective factors that makes the ball approach the field and near the opponent's goal and eventually the ball becomes a goal. For this reason, the TNT team also paid attention to the pass and worked on it. In the following, we will explain how to implement the pass in our team.

2.1 Normal pass

Our normal pass is almost similar to last year's pass, where each player draws small circles to her teammates if she wants to pass then (Figure 1), according to the distance of the opponent's players from the circles and a series of other parameters, they choose the best player and give him a pass.

Fig. 1. The image of the circles drawn to the opponent's players

2.2 Forward pass

We added this pass to our team this year and it still has many problems, but now it has improved our performance and we use it. This pass is in such a way that each player has eight circles around him (Figure 2), and in the right conditions, the player who has the ball chooses which one he wants to pass to according to a series of parameters.

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the action that occurs

3 Offensive operations

Like real football, in order to score a goal and win the game, every team needs a good attacking strategist, who actually needs to fix small parts such as player alignment, dribbling, etc. in order to finally be able to to flower . In the following sections, we will discuss and describe the method we use so that you can understand it better.

3.1 The arrangement of the players

Definitely, the arrangement of the players and their type of movement in the game has a great impact on the outcome of the game . For example, a team that exchanges better passes can keep the ball longer, and as a result, the probability of scoring a goal is much lower. It is very difficult and almost impossible to implement what happens in real football, but recently, stronger teams have received various data using artificial intelligence and machine learning, and by analyzing them, it helps a lot to determine the location of players. Unfortunately, our team has not yet succeeded in using artificial intelligence and is using another method . We have marked one hundred and ten points on the playing field and given them to the Fedite software, the ball was closer to each of the marked points, according to that point, the player will be in the arrangement that has been determined in advance. Of course, this method has many flaws that we are going to use another method in the future.

3.2 Dribble

Undoubtedly, dribbling is very important in the game because the possibility of error is very high and there are many methods, each of which has its own advantages and disadvantages. The TNT team uses a completely new method, which fortunately has been very useful. Now we will describe it.

First, we draw a circle around each player and we draw eight triangles in that circle (Figure 3). In certain situations, the player first checks which two adjacent triangles have no opposing players then it goes to the common vertex of two triangles. But if there were no such triangles and only one triangle was empty of the opposing players, then it goes to the middle of the base of the middle of that triangle. The numbers you see on the image determine the priority

Fig. 3. Schematic form of segmentation and figure drawing

4 Conclusion

In this article, we discussed parts of the TNT team's playing methods and told what changes we made in the team compared to last year. We also talked a little about the history of the TNT team and...

References

1. Sayareh A, Zare N, Amini O, Firouzkouhi A, Sarvmaili M, Matwin S. Observation Denoising in CYRUS Soccer Simulation 2D Team For RoboCup 2023. arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.19283. 2023 May 27.
2. Zare N, Sayareh A, Sarvmaili M, Amini O, Soares A, Matwin S. CYRUS soccer simulation 2D team description paper 2021. arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.02310. 2022 Jun 6.
3. Yamaguchi, M., Kuga, R., Omori, H., Fukushima, T., Nakashima, T., Akiyama, H.: Helios2021: Team description paper. In: RoboCup 2021 Symposium and Competi-

- tions, Worldwide (2021).
4. Gabel, T., Sommer, F., Breuer, S., Godehardt, E.: FRA-UNited–team description 2019. In: RoboCup 2019 Symposium and Competitions: Team Description Papers. Sydney, Australia (2019).
 5. Marian, S., Luca, D., Sarac, B., Cotarlea, O.: OXSY 2018 Team Description. In: RoboCup 2018 Symposium and Competitions: Team Description Papers. Montreal, Canada (2018).
 6. Marian, S., Luca, D., Sarac, B., Cotarlea, O.: OXSY 2018 Team Description. In: RoboCup 2018 Symposium and Competitions: Team Description Papers. Montreal, Canada (2018).
 7. Noohpisheh, M., Shekarriz, M., Zaremehjardi, F., Khademi Ardekani, F. and Khorsand, S.A., 2021. Persepolis soccer 2D simulation team description paper 2021. In RoboCup 2021 Symposium and Competitions: Team Description Papers. Worldwide.
 8. Noohpisheh, M., Shekarriz, M., Bordbar, A., Liaghat, M., Salimi, A., Borzoo, D., Zarei, A.: Razi Soccer 2D Simulation Team Description Paper 2019. In: RoboCup 2019 Symposium and Competitions: Team Description Papers. Sydney, Australia (2019).
 9. Fabro, João Alberto, Álefe Felipe Gonçalves Pereira Dias, Eli Teixeira Paula Júnior, Gabriel Rauta Buiar, Misael Rosa da Costa, Luis Paulo Reis, and Nuno Lau. "FCP_GPR_2019 Soccer Simulation 2D Team Description Paper."
 10. Coimbra, Felipe, Miguel Neto, Camila Rapereda, Guilherme Marinot, Cláudio Silva, and Matheus Marcontes. "ITAndroids 2D Soccer Simulation Team Description Paper 2017." *Aeronautics Institute of Technology, Sao Jose dos Campos, Sao Paulo, Brazil.*